

**LINGUISTIC MEANS OF EXPRESSING A COMPLIMENT
IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN**

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Annotation. This article is devoted to study of speech which gives general definitions of speech acts in Modern linguistics. In addition, it discusses a compliment as a speech act, three main elements are distinguished: speech action, psychological interaction and a way of linguistic implementation of speech action.

Key words: speech act, grammar, phonetics, phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, discourse, constative utterance.

As we know that a speech act is an utterance that serves a function in communication. We perform speech acts when we offer an apology, greeting, request, complaint, invitation, compliment, or refusal. A speech act might contain just one word, as in "Sorry!" to perform an apology, or several words or sentences: "I'm sorry I forgot your birthday. I just let it slip my mind." Speech acts include real-life interactions and require not only knowledge of the language but also appropriate use of that language within a given culture.

Here are some examples of speech acts we use or hear every day:

Greeting: "Hi, Eric. How are things going?"

Request: "Could you pass me the mashed potatoes, please?"

Complaint: "I've already been waiting three weeks for the computer, and I was told it would be delivered within a week."

Invitation: "We're having some people over Saturday evening and wanted to know if you'd like to join us."

Compliment: "Hey, I really like your tie!"

Refusal: "Oh, I'd love to see that movie with you but this Friday just isn't going to work."

Speech acts are difficult to perform in a second language because learners may not know the idiomatic expressions or cultural norms in the second language or they may transfer their first language rules and conventions into the second language, assuming that such rules are universal. Because the natural tendency for language learners is to fall back on what they know to be appropriate in their first language, it is important that these learners understand exactly what they do in that first language in order to be able to recognize what is transferable to

other languages. Something that works in English might not transfer in meaning when translated into the second language. For example, the following remark as uttered by a native English speaker could easily be misinterpreted by a native Chinese hearer:

Sarah: "I couldn't agree with you more. "

Cheng: "Hmmm...." (Thinking: "She couldn't agree with me? I thought she liked my idea!")

An example of potential misunderstanding for an American learner of Japanese would be what is said by a dinner guest in Japan to thank the host. For the invitation and the meal the guests may well apologize a number of times in addition to using an expression of gratitude (arigatou gosaimasu) -- for instance, for the intrusion into the private home (sumimasen ojama shimasu), the commotion that they are causing by getting up from the table (shitsurei shimasu), and also for the fact that they put their host out since they had to cook the meal, serve it, and will have to do the dishes once the guests have left (sumimasen). American guests might think this to be rude or inappropriate and choose to compliment the host on the wonderful food and festive atmosphere, or thank the host for inviting them, unaware of the social conventions involved in performing such a speech act in Japanese. Although such compliments or expression of thanks are also appropriate in Japanese, they are hardly enough for native speakers of Japanese -- not without a few apologies!

Considering a compliment as a speech act, three main elements are distinguished: speech action, psychological interaction and a way of linguistic implementation of speech action.

Let us first note the fact that the speech act is understood by us as a kind of communicative action, structural unit of language communication following J. L. Austin, J. R. Searle, E. V. Paducheva, N. D. Arutyunova and others. The model of speech action itself integrates the provisions of the theory of speech acts, the theory of speech activity and the concept of politeness. Complimentary statement is a language tool achieving qualitatively different communicative goals (verbal and non-verbal), for example, the implementation speech act, which is the unity of locutionary, illocutionary, perlocutionary acts and some social action.

As for the illocutionary purposes of a compliment, they are to express the following, and namely: the speaker's positive intentional state, the representative content of which is an explicit or implicit positive value judgment; intention/aspiration/desire the speaker to please the addressee;

positive attitude of the speaker to the addressee. Necessary also emphasize that the illocutionary act of a compliment is characterized by a wide range of expressed intentional states of the speaker, such as approval, admiration, sympathy, respect, affection, love, pleasure, enjoyment, etc. With regard to the perlocutionary purpose of a compliment, we can say that it consists in causing the recipient a positive emotional reaction. The impact that a compliment has on the addressee is associated with the satisfaction of one of his most important needs - to be recognized and appreciated by the people around.

So, compliments are social actions that are divided into two main classes: these are ket and instrumental. In this case, the classification criterion is the nature of the social goal compliment. The social goal of all etiquette compliments is to maintain non-antagonistic relations between communicants, while the invariant goal of instrumental compliments is to change communication partner behavior. Thus, a compliment involves a social and emotional speech impact. Social speech impact involves special situations of communication in which there is no transmission of information as such, but certain social acts are carried out, for example, an attempt to arrange the interlocutor to himself, express his admiration for his talent and virtues, force him to carry out some actions, etc. Emotional speech impact is aimed at interpersonal subjective emotional relationships.

As we know, compliments combine the characteristics of different speech acts. So, they can combine the features of representatives, expressiveness and actual communication. However, the main characteristic compliment is its evaluative nature, therefore it is considered by us in the category of expressiveness. A compliment refers to non-informative speech actions, expressing regulative, indexical and emotional and evaluative content [1, p. 180-183].

Summarizing all the above, we accept the definition of the speech act of praise / compliment as a separate speech statement that serves to express an opinion (more often positive and less often - pseudo-positive) of the addressee about his addressee or about a third person who is not a direct participant in communication, and is pronounced in the conditions of direct communication of the interlocutors to achieve addresser of specific goals.

The criteria for typology of speech acts of praise/compliment are:

- direct orientation of the statement to the addressee, present in the communicative space, acting as the recipient of the compliment;

- indirect orientation of the statement to the addressee present in the communicative space, acting as a recipient of a compliment, but not a participant in the interaction;
- the direction of the statement to the addressee of the compliment, which is absent in the communicative space (at the same time, the addressee participates in interaction with another subject
- the addressee of the statement of a non-complimentary nature);
- the direction of the compliment on the addresser (if the addresser and the addressee coincide in one person) in interaction with another subject (the addressee of the non-complimentary speech statement);
- focus of the compliment on a single or multiple (collective) addressee;
- the focus of the compliment on the internal or external characteristics of the addressee;
- set and non-set of compliments;
- stylization or non-stylization of a compliment;
- consistency / inconsistency of the deep and surface semantics of the compliment;
- compliment or pseudo-compliment [3, p. 2-3].

In speech acts of praise/compliment, the national and cultural characteristics of the English and Russian ethnic communities can be expressed as follows: in the objects of compliments; in its addressees and addressees; in ways to implement a compliment; in the language design of a compliment; with regard to compliment and response. These criteria were taken by us as the basis for the classification of a compliment and analysis of the general patterns and distinctive features of the implementation of the considered speech acts in English and Russian communicative cultures.

As for the classification according to the objects of compliments, both in English and in Russian There are the following types of compliments:

- compliments to the appearance of a person;
- compliments evaluating professionalism or certain abilities;
- generalizing compliments (compliments that characterize the personality as a whole);
- compliments to internal, moral qualities;
- compliments to intellectual abilities;
- other compliments (compliments concerning age, compliment of the name,
- compliment of the dwelling, home environment and others) [2, p. 1-5].

It was revealed that in the communicative culture of Russia, compliments to the appearance of a person dominate, and in the communicative culture of England, compliments to the moral qualities of a person prevail. It is believed that the main factors influencing such national and cultural differences in the use of compliments are different value systems and norms of English and Russian etiquette. Nevertheless, in English speech communication, compliments on appearance are given great attention. This type of compliment takes second place in English culture. Of course, both in Russian and in English communicative culture, compliments related to appearance are used mainly in informal communication. As for business communication, compliments about a person's appearance are used quite rarely, but are often considered as a sign of bad taste[4].

Despite this fact, this kind of speech act of praise/compliment is still present in both communicative cultures: "Denis was not just a promising object, which is any young and single comrade in a predominantly female team, but also in general an interesting man. Women look at such women regardless of their own prospects, even if their personal life is completely arranged" (Berseneva A. "Last Eve").

"She was in her mid-twenties, with a lively, intelligent face, a full, sensuous mouth, sparkling eyes that could change from a soft moss green to a dark jade in moments, and a trim, athletic figure" (Sheldon S. "If Tomorrow Comes").

Regarding the compliments to the internal qualities of a person, most often used in English, we can say that the most productive are compliments to kindness, generosity, modesty, courage, religiosity, honesty, for example:

"...I could tell you were an honest man. There weren't so many left" (Lodge D. "Paradise News").

However, the above character traits are universal, so we can not talk about monopoly possession of this or that ethnic community by the specified characteristics. Necessary to note the differences in the forms of their manifestation and their assessment by the English and Russian linguistic personality. Then just as in English examples the assessment of a person's moral qualities is expressed explicitly, in Russian statements praise (compliment) can be expressed indirectly, somewhat in a veiled form, like traits, distinguishing the recipient of a compliment from other people: "This is a very good boy. Serious, kind, honest" (Marinina A. "Coincidence").

Compliments that evaluate the abilities and professionalism of a person occupy one of the leading positions in the English communicative culture. The most common compliments to a high level of competence at work are:

"...they've done a beautiful job on the restoration" (Lodge D. "Paradise News").

In Russian, compliments to the abilities and professionalism of a person are also found, but not much less often:

"Well, I don't have a person who is better than you who could handle this!" (Dotsenko V. "Justice of the Madman").

Much less often than in English, compliments are also used in Russian communicative culture and intellectual human abilities, however, in both cultures they are still represented:

"... you are a very smart and developed girl ..." (Marinina A. "The one who knows");

"You're so intelligent!" (Updike J. "Couples").

So, the list of objects of speech acts of praise/compliment is very diverse. However, numerous studies carried out in this area make it possible to single out the most typical object orientation of compliments for English and Russian communicative cultures. It should be emphasized that there are different manifestations of evaluativeness in the communicative consciousness of the English and Russians, as well as differences in the focus of complimenting in these communicative cultures. For the British internal factors play an important role. This is manifested in the frequent use of compliments to the intellect and moral qualities of a person. Russians in communication pay attention mainly to external factors. This confirms the productivity in the Russian communicative culture of compliments on appearance, as well as praise for a job well done.

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